

The Importance of Studying Indonesian Language

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ABSTRACT

This article was written to provide information about the importance of learning Indonesian in higher education. Indonesian is a national language that must be preserved and its rules must be observed. The use of Indonesian still experiences many inaccuracies because we are not aware of the importance of paying attention to rules, spelling and accuracy in writing and pronunciation of Indonesian. The correct use of Indonesian is intensively introduced from elementary school to university. By introducing the use of good language, it is hoped that it will foster a sense of love for the Indonesian nation and become a shared responsibility to apply it in everyday life, one of which is in academic and educational environments.

INTRODUCTION

Language is an identity that is used as a means of communication between individuals. Indonesian is the language of unity. Indonesia consists of 17,000 islands and 718 regional languages that surround them. In the past, before Indonesian was designated as the national language, the Indonesian people communicated with their own regional language which was passed down from generation to generation. The vast Indonesian nation with many regional languages hampers communication between nations on different islands. The beginning of the history of the Indonesian language was born in the youth oath on October 28 1928 and then confirmed as the national language. The Indonesian language developed into the identity and spearhead of the founding of the Indonesian State. As stated in the youth oath, we, the Indonesian people, claim to share the blood of one Indonesian homeland, one nation, namely the Indonesian nation, and uphold the language of unity, namely Indonesian. Indonesian is closely related to society because the existence of this language fosters an attitude of love for the nation, respect for the homeland, and there are no differences in terms of communication.

Language makes communication and all our activities easier. Humans as creatures who cannot live alone certainly cannot be separated from communication. Communication is an activity carried out either verbally or verbally with the aim of understanding ALINEA: Journal of Language, Literature and Teaching |115 the meaning of the information conveyed by other people. Therefore, as Indonesian citizens, it is best to use the correct Indonesian language in order to create national unity & unity. The author chose the title the importance of Indonesian in higher education because knowledge of the good use of Indonesian has many benefits in the field of education. In higher education, the language is used to create scientific works, research proposals, papers, and the importance of Indonesian is as a means of communication between students and teachers. By uniting the language, the knowledge received and taught will be easily understood and absorbed by students and for teachers it will be easier to convey the material. Indonesian has many benefits that really help us in everyday life. So the author chose this topic because the author is aware that Indonesian must be taught and used well so that it is not covered by slang.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

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METHODOLOGY

The method in this article is subjective descriptive, namely a method that explains, describes and presents an overview of the importance of Indonesian in higher education. The source for the preparation was obtained using library study techniques. The library study technique is the collection of information sought and understood from reading sources such as books, articles, journals, scientific works and other sources that support writing. In this article, we will explain the importance of using Indonesian in higher education, explaining the role, function and benefits of learning Indonesian in higher education.

RESEARCH RESULTS & DISCUSSION

1. Indonesian language lessons have been a mandatory subject since we were in elementary school to college.

The government ensures that Indonesian is a compulsory subject because Indonesian is a unifying nation, tribe and culture in Indonesia. The presence of Indonesian creates harmony without having to forget the regional language. Nowadays, the application of appropriate language is experiencing a setback due to the development of slang. Many students do not understand the rules for writing or pronouncing Indonesian according to the rules because they think slang is easier to pronounce and more flexible.

The government has made this subject a mandatory subject so that students continue to use it, such as when writing scientific papers. Indonesian looks easy but is actually a rich language. Writing Indonesian must pay attention to rules and regulations. Rules used in Indonesian:

- a. Spelling rules.
Regulations regarding the pronunciation of a word/sentence and the use of capital letters, italics or acronyms.
- b. Morphological rules. Rules regarding word formation such as compound words, repeated words, and affixes
- c. Syntactic rules. Rules that regulate the relationship between words d. Semantic rules.

Pay attention to instructions and rules. Instructions used in Indonesian:

- a. Spelling hint. Settings regarding the pronunciation of a word or sentence and using capital letters, italics.
- b. Morphological clues. Instructions regarding word formation such as various words, repeat words, and affixes
- c. Syntax hints. Instructions that regulate the relationship between words.

The rules also determine the meaning of a word. Understanding language, language is a system of sound symbols used by a society to work together and be concerned (Puspitasari, 2017).

The nature of Munurut Mulyati's language (a) is systematic, that is, it consists of patterns that are regular and interconnected; b) arbitrary, i.e. arbitrary form and meaning according to the user; (c) conventional, i.e. form and meaning are determined based on community agreement; (d) dynamic, namely the form and meaning develop/change according to development. Language is based on rules and methods that cannot be violated so that ongoing communication is not disrupted. Design rules, rules and patterns include sound systems, form order and sentence order. For communication to run well, the recipient and sender of the language must master it. The position and function of the Indonesian language. Indonesian has a very important place in people's lives in Indonesia. Indonesia is a country consisting of several ethnic groups. Every ethnic group has a regional language.

In its position as a national language, Indonesian has the function of (1) a symbol of national pride, (2) a symbol of national identity, (3) a means of communication between citizens, between regions and between cultures, and (4) a tool that enables the unification of various ethnic groups with different backgrounds. their respective socio-cultural and linguistic backgrounds into a unified Indonesian nation. As a symbol of pride, Indonesian shows social and cultural values that are fundamental to a sense of nationality (Umar, 2017). Indonesian is a symbol of the nation's identity, and must be preserved in order to have an identity. As a place of communication between people, regions and ethnic groups, Indonesian is an important place for speakers in Indonesia so that everyone can freely explore places in Indonesia without having difficulty understanding the language.

Indonesian plays a big role as (1) the official national language (2) the language of education, (3) a tool for communicating at the national level and planning and implementing development, (4) a tool for developing culture, science and technology. As the country's official language, Indonesian is used both orally and in writing in various government events. As the language of education in the world of education, Indonesian is used in educational settings from childhood to universities throughout Indonesia. Related to the third function, Indonesian is a tool that connects the national level to plan and implement national development, for the benefit of the government. Like other things, Indonesian is the only thing that allows Indonesia to foster and develop a national culture so that it has its own characteristics and identification, which differentiate it from regional culture.

Functions of Indonesian as a language that has had basic functions since its founding. This function makes the Indonesian language grow and be known by other countries. Indonesian has a basic function as (1) a unifying tool, (2) as a link between people from different regions, (3) the identity/identification of the Indonesian nation. Indonesian language unites the nation. Indonesian language unites various differences in Indonesia (Rahardi, M. H, 2009). Indonesia has islands spread from Sabang Island to Merauke. Indonesian combines all its

unique qualities and cultures into one without any differences. Indonesian as a unifier between communities. Indonesia also has hundreds of regional languages with unique characteristics. Each island in Indonesia also has its own regional communication method which is expressed within its regional scope. For example, the island of North Sumatra and the capital city of Medan use the regional language of Medan to communicate. In the province of North Sumatra there are many regional languages in it such as Malay, Toba Batak, Mandailing, Karo, Simalungung, Nias, Pakpak and Pesisir Sibolga-Central Tapanulis.

With so many forms of communication on Medan Island, communication becomes slow between people with different languages. If a person speaks Batak language to someone who speaks Malay, then the person who speaks Malay will find it difficult to understand the meaning of the words of the person who speaks Batak language and vice versa. So Indonesian was determined to be the national language to facilitate communication and make it easier to understand the intentions of the person communicating. Indonesian as a national identity. Identity is self-identity.

Indonesian becomes an identity if the Indonesian people use it and make it unique. Indonesian has become an identity so that it is easily recognized by other countries. Indonesian is widely known by various countries and is used as a form of learning, such as Vietnam, Japan, Ukraine and South Korea.

Indonesian Language Courses for Students Indonesian is a language product that was born in the Indonesian nation itself. Indonesian was not just born, but also through a long process. Even now, Indonesian is still being developed according to the times. In this way, Indonesian vocabulary can increase over time. Rapid developments, especially in this era of globalization, require the Indonesian language to always improve so that it can accommodate various new terms that are not found in Indonesian. Indonesian is used to unite the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). Because the Indonesian nation has various tribes, each of which has its own regional language. Therefore, Indonesian can be an effort to unite these differences by being guided by Indonesian. Apart from that, Indonesian has one function, namely as a standard language for writing papers. Good and correct Indonesian is recommended for writing scientific articles. English must be used as an international language. However, the scientific article must also be written in Indonesian so that many parties can read the article without exception. can also study the article.

In the era of globalization, the era of advances in information and communication technology, every individual must contribute their creativity and express it in writing. Especially for students who are always faced with doing work in written form. However, it turns out that in the world of writing there is still a lot of confusion among students who still don't understand how to write well. Apart from that, the culture of writing according to EYD rules is often forgotten because of the rapid development of technology and computing (Damayanti, 2010). Apart from that, enthusiasm for writing is decreasing, so it is not surprising that students prefer to copy other people's work or buy the work of people who claim it as their own. In fact, developments in technology

and computing have provided the widest possibilities for humans to continue working and expressing all kinds of creativity, especially in written form.

For example, in the internet world there is a lot of information that can expand knowledge and understanding, and is a place that is ready to accept all human creativity and ideas in written form. Among students at this time, there are still many initiatives in writing that are relatively low, so this has an impact on the results of the scientific work that is compiled, causing many errors related to the correct writing system. However, of course, students who have gone through elementary to high school have received Indonesian language lessons from A to Z. And are these universities just repeating material that has already been taught like in schools? Based on these results, lecturers usually teach course material delivered by Indonesian language teachers from elementary to high school. The lecturers returned to teach Indonesian grammar, general tips for correcting spelling, and general terminology tips.

Often students are made like students in the Indonesian Language Department at the Faculty of Letters and Languages. It is as if they are being educated to become prospective linguists or prospective Indonesian language scholars. Many first year students take Indonesian language courses with only one and a half steps or feel pressured by grades or points because they have been given the same material before. So it is not surprising that students experience boredom in learning Indonesian. The Importance of Indonesian in Higher Education Indonesian is the national language of Indonesia which is a unifying language.

Indonesian is taught from elementary school, middle school and high school. Therefore, it is good if school children can master Indonesian. At least after high school level you have sufficient knowledge of Indonesian (Widi, 2014). However, in reality there are still some students who can speak Indonesian completely. At university we learn Indonesian, but we have to maintain it. This requires a lot of youthful and foreign cultural influences that tend to influence the minds of the younger generation. Apart from that, Indonesian really needs to be used as teaching material at universities because every student at these universities usually comes from various regions in Indonesia. Then Indonesian functions as a guide in compiling and using good and correct grammar in scientific communication. (dissertation, thesis, dissertation, etc.). Apart from that, learning Indonesian in higher education for students is the same as learning Indonesian. in high school, but conversations in college are more specific and in-depth, and most students still want to learn Indonesian because they can speak the language well and correctly.

Because there are still many errors in language writing, the Director General of the Indonesian Ministry of National Education decided to include Indonesian as one of the mandatory subjects in all universities and all departments. This aims to improve the quality of language and develop the students' personalities. We as Indonesian citizens (WNI) are required to have the skills to use Indonesian according to its rules so that the authenticity of the Indonesian language can be maintained. Academic work is often done at universities. Students not only create scientific articles, but also various other

forms of written work. In the Indonesian language course we will find material to understand the importance of Enhanced Spelling and Spelling (EYD) techniques in writing scientific papers.

We must be able to use good diction and effective sentences according to our educational level, not like high school and middle school students. In a scientific work, the use of language has a very important meaning. Language is a means of human lingual communication, both verbal and written. To use language in a scientific work means emphasizing language as a means of communication in the form of writing. Therefore, the use of language in scientific work is very important.

Scientific work has the meaning of a written work that contains a discussion of something written by a researcher. Scientific works have various types such as journal articles and research reports. All of this has its essence and is the result of scientific activity. The papers given to students tend to be conclusions based on thoughts written by experts and then they take the important points. The practice of writing reports is assigned to students as a way for students to have the ability to develop ideas and express their creativity in written form. Apart from that, for the reasons above, there are several other things that make Indonesian a subject at university. Thus, it is very important to hold Indonesian language courses in every university, apart from the fact that Indonesian is the language of our own country and as a unifying language, in this way we also indirectly preserve our language. Who else will preserve the Indonesian language if not us as citizens of the country itself.

The Indonesian language course is taught not without reason but because it has the following functions: 1) Creating a loyal attitude towards the Indonesian language, which is expected to encourage students to maintain the Indonesian language; 2) Fostering pride in the Indonesian language, which is expected to encourage students to prioritize their language and use it as a symbol of national identity; and 3) Growing and maintaining awareness of the existence of Indonesian language norms, which will hopefully encourage students to use Indonesian in accordance with applicable rules and regulations (Asih, 2016).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Indonesian consists of the absorption of the Malay language from the time of trade in Indonesia. Indonesia consists of hundreds of islands with unique regional languages in them. Indonesian is the nation's identity, a benchmark for language use. Indonesian as communication helps Indonesian citizens to understand the information conveyed by the person they are speaking to. The implementation of Indonesian as a mandatory subject in the educational environment is expected to foster a sense of pride in one's homeland. The Indonesian language should not be forgotten but must be preserved and continuously introduced to foreign cultures. The richness of Indonesian will increase interest in other countries to learn it. Students are the generation that will make the nation proud in the future and should use Indonesian according to their place. If you are in a family environment, use

polite language. If you are at school and communicating with peers, use relaxed language. Place the use of language according to where the language is spoken. With this, it is hoped that the love for Indonesian will increase because by applying the language well we have united the nation without any gaps in communication. Indonesian is an identity and also a national characteristic that must be preserved and carried forward to the next generation.

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